

1 **Trastuzumab resistance features PLXNC1 activation.**

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6 We studied whole tumor gene expression in humans with pathologic complete response (pCR) or
7 residual disease (RD) following treatment for HER2+ breast cancer to discover gene expression changes
8 associated with, resulting from or causing resistance to treatment with the HER2-targeted treatment
9 trastuzumab (Herceptin). We identified activation of PLXNC1 in humans whose tumors display resistance
10 to treatment with trastuzumab. Studying whole transcription in HER2+ breast cancer cells engineered to
11 develop trastuzumab-resistance *in vitro* validated this phenomena. PLXNC1 activation likely supports
12 resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.
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